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- Provenances from drier areas performed better than those from more humid

**Prescribed fire effects on early recruitment of Mediterranean pine species
depend on fire exposure and seed provenance**

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Abstract

Prescribed fires are becoming a more widely used forest management tool to reduce both fuel load for fire prevention and high-severity wildfires. However, alterations to site conditions and influence on the natural regeneration of these fires in Mediterranean pine forests are still poorly known. Our study investigates how using prescribed fires before or after natural pine seed release could influence changes in germination and individuals' early survival by altering the composition and structure of these Mediterranean habitats. We ran a seed-sowing experiment to analyse the recruitment patterns of three Mediterranean pine species (*Pinus halepensis*, *Pinus pinaster* and *Pinus nigra*) in three sites where prescribed burns were carried out. In each site, we sowed one representative pine species according to natural habitats. Three treatments (control: sowing without intervention; pre-fire: sowing before prescribed burns; and post-fire: sowing after prescribed burns) were established. In the sown experiment, we tested two biogeographical seed provenances (wetter and drier regions) per species to observe different capabilities of adaptation. Germination and survival of individuals were monitored during one year. We observed that the provenances from drier areas had higher germination and survival rates than those from the wetter ones. The three species seemed to undergo a negative growth effect in the burned plots. Within the burned area, the pre-fire seeds presented higher germination and early survival rates than post-fire. These outcomes could be useful in fire management planning as a tool to influence forest regeneration.

Keywords: seed germination; seedling survival; Mediterranean pine forest; prescribed fire planning; ecological restoration; fire management

1 Introduction

Mediterranean terrestrial ecosystems are landscapes clearly influenced by natural disturbances, such as droughts and wildfires (Keeley et al., 2011). Changes in land use, mainly agricultural land abandonment and massive unmanaged reforestations, have led to more continuous, dense and fire-prone forest stands (Pausas, 2004; Poyatos et al., 2009). Increasing available fuel load, together with fire suppression policies, have triggered changes in fire regimes by promoting greater recurrence and severity of wildfires in recent decades (Flannigan et al., 2009).

In this context, using tools like prescribed fires is being gradually more common in Mediterranean forests to reduce high fuel load and to, hence, minimise the risk of fire propagation. Forest services have found in prescribed fires an efficient ally to lessen the impact of the total areas burned in fires and their severity (Casals et al., 2016). Fire regime restoration has also promoted the regeneration of fire-adapted or fire-dependent species (Pollet and Omi, 2002). Nevertheless, other issues like social awareness, population distribution and land use still limit the use of this tool (Fernandes et al., 2013). Differences in intensity between wildfires and prescribed fires can lead to study outcomes that may not be applicable to prescribed fires (Pausas and Fernández-Muñoz, 2012). The implementation of these controlled fires is normally made beyond the natural fire season, which poses questions as to the effects and consequences of fires on key ecological processes. Therefore, these prescribed burns influence regeneration and recruitment dynamics, which could trigger changes in other ecosystem processes and highlights the necessity of a climate change adaptation strategy for adaptive forest management (Goldman, 2010). Wildfires negatively impact pine species by significantly lowering the likelihood of germination (Alvarez et al., 2005; Reyes and Casal, 2004). They also reduce the germination and establishment of seedlings, compared with ground fires or low-severity fires, by significantly affecting post-burn recruitment (Martínez et al.,

2002). Although *Pinus pinaster* Ait. and *Pinus halepensis* Mill. dissemination may be benefited by fire, their seeds are not heat-stimulated (Escudero et al., 1999; Ferrandis et al., 1996). Adaptive responses of Mediterranean pines to fire are well-known in species like *Pinus halepensis* and *P. pinaster*, which bear serotinous cones that disperse seeds after fires, as well as *Pinus nigra* Arn. ssp *salzmanii*, which develops a thick bark to provide protection against fire (de las Heras et al., 2012; Retana et al., 2012).

Forest management strategies rely on predictable tree regeneration to ensure ecosystem persistence, and an adequate degree of ecosystem stability. Moreover, climate changes are expected to affect wildfire frequency and intensity (Stocker et al., 2013), which may thus reduce natural regeneration success by requiring adjustments to silvicultural practices to be made (Bravo-Oviedo et al., 2014). The first development stages of trees are known to be one of the most limiting stages in the life of a stand (Ordóñez et al., 2004). Natural germination and early establishment are the most constraining factors, and also the most important mechanisms to determine forest structure (Dalling et al., 2002). Changing these environmental conditions due to climate change or the occurrence of natural disturbances like wildfires means that it is even more crucial to use adapted species, provenances and genotypes as they are more resilient to these upcoming variabilities in management programs (Alía et al., 1997; Garzón et al., 2011; Ghalambor et al., 2007). Natural ground and prescribed fires can alter ecosystem conditions by limiting or promoting the establishment of regeneration. Some studies have also suggested that conifer recruitment may benefit from prescribed burns (Certini, 2005; Ryan et al., 2013). At the same time, temperatures from prescribed fires may trigger the dissemination of seeds of serotinous pines. It is known that some seeds need heat scarification to achieve better germination success rates (Ferrandis et al., 1999; Martínez-Sánchez et al., 1995), although the seeds affected by high temperatures present

lower germination rates in many cases (Alvarez et al., 2007). Predation also plays an important role in these early stages, which limit successful regeneration (Lucas-Borja et al., 2010; Ordóñez et al., 2004). Prescribed fires can affect population dynamics by altering canopy cover, soil nutrients, soil moisture, water repellence and infiltration rates. These changes are more intense on the superficial soil layer and at the soil-litter interface, where seeds and seedlings obtain their resources (Ryan et al., 2013).

According to this basis, the key goal of this study was to evaluate the influence of prescribed fires on the early natural recruitment of *P. halepensis*, *P. pinaster* and *P. nigra* to provide the information needed so that these forest management practices can be applied to Mediterranean ecosystems. For this purpose, our secondary objectives were to study seed germination and seedling growth responses on three different sites depending on three treatments (Control, Pre-fire and Post-fire) to assess the relationship between burning timing and seed dispersal timing. Different seed provenances were also tested to trial the influence of ecotype (seeds from drier and wetter provenances) on regeneration after these treatments.

2 Material and Methods

Study area

We studied the post-burn germination and early survival of three Mediterranean pines in three locations in the central-eastern Iberian Peninsula. *Pinus halepensis*, *P. pinaster* and *P. nigra* were sown respectively at each site to observe their performance in germination and early survival terms (during a 1-year study). Hence there were three sites located in three forests within an

altitudinal and climatic range (Sites): one located in the south-eastern part of the Iberian Peninsula, dominated by *P. halepensis* (PH) and characterized by a dry climate; an intermediate site located in a subhumid climate and characterized by *P. pinaster* (PP); and the highest site situated in a humid climate and dominated by *P. nigra* (PN) (detailed information in Table 1).

Figure 1. a) Map of the Iberian Peninsula with the three study sites location; b) Case of the study plots location at the *P. nigra* site; c) Example of seeding units distribution within a plot; d) Seeding unit schematic illustration in a burned area with drier and wetter provenances; and Pre (simulating dispersion prior to fire) and Post (simulating dispersion postfire). Terms are as described in the text.

Table 1. Description of the three sites located. Mean annual temperature (MET); Mean lowest temperatures of the coldest month (ML); Mean highest temperatures of the hottest month (MH).

Species of study	<i>Pinus halepensis</i>	<i>Pinus pinaster</i>	<i>Pinus nigra</i>
Characteristics			
Location	Beteta (40°33'02.9"N 2°06'32.6"W)	El Pozuelo (40°33'53.5"N 2°16'30.4"W)	Lezuza (38°54'21.9"N 2°20'13.9"W)
Main species in the site	Pure <i>Pinus nigra</i> stand	<i>Pinus nigra</i> and <i>Pinus pinaster</i> mixed stand	<i>Pinus pinaster</i> and <i>Pinus halepensis</i> mixed stand
Understory species	<i>Genista scorpius</i> L. <i>Arctostaphylos uva-ursi</i> L. <i>Juniperus communis</i> L. <i>Rosa canina</i> L. <i>Amelanchier ovalis</i> Medik. <i>Lavandula</i> sp. <i>Thymus</i> sp.	<i>Quercus faginea</i> Lam. <i>Cistus laurifolius</i> L. <i>Berberis vulgaris</i> L. <i>Rosa canina</i> L. <i>Genista Scorpius</i> L.	<i>Quercus ilex</i> subsp. <i>ballota</i> <i>Quercus faginea</i> Lam. <i>Quercus coccifera</i> L. <i>Juniperus oxycedrus</i> L. <i>Thymus</i> sp. <i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i> L.
Tree density (trees/ha)	1281 ±256	667 ±125	595 ±141
DBH (cm)	20.6 ±12.7	18.7 ±8.7	19.3 ±11.2
Average height (m)	7.25 ±3.2	7.49 ±3.6	5.25 ±1.9
MET; ML; MH (°C)	10.2; 1.7; 20.1	11.3; 2.7; 23	13.5; - 0.9; 31.8
Soil type	Clay	Sandy-loam	Clay
Slope (%)	10 ± 2	5 ± 2	4 ± 1
Aspect	Northeast	North	Northwest
Prescribed burn soil-litter interface T^o (°C)	361±29	264±62	260±25
Altitudinal range (m.a.s.l.)	1250 - 1300	1000 - 1050	1010 – 1040
Annual precipitation (mm)	946	700	456

Experimental design

For each of three study sites, we placed six 50 m-side quadrat plots (2,500 m²). In all these plots, we established an inner 30-m side (900 m²) to prevent the edge effect of starting the fire. In each sites, three plots were left unburned as the control (no treatment), and three others were fire-treated (Figure 1b). A prior characterization of the stands was made to assure relative homogeneity in variables such as forest cover, tree species, shrubs cover, shrubs/herbaceous species, slope, aspect, tree density, tree diameter and tree age. In spring 2016, the Fire Extinction Services of Castilla-La Mancha performed controlled fires to reduce fuel load and the risk of large high-severity fires. Burning temperatures were monitored using HOBO thermocouple type K (0°C-1250°C ($\pm 4.0^\circ\text{C}$)) with insulated 30-AWG wire (less than 0.2 cm in diameter), assembled on Data Loggers UX120-014M (Onset Corp., Bourne (MA), Australia) and placed on the litter surface, soil surface and at a depth of 2 cm (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Photographs taken during the prescribed fires, the post-fire situation and seedlings in a Control plot 2 months after sowing.

The average temperatures recorded during the prescribed burns were 314°C (SE= 37) on the litter surface, 72°C (SE= 22) on the soil surface, and 19°C (SE= 1) at 2 cm belowground. The time of residence for temperatures above 60°C and 100°C was 126 (SE= 23) and 24 (SE= 6) seconds, respectively.

Three treatments were defined for the study: Control: unburned seeding units where seeds were sown in unburned plots to examine natural germination and early survival rates; Pre: seeds were sown in burned plots immediately before fire passage, which means that these seeds were fire-treated by simulating natural seed dispersion before a prescribed fire; post-fire: seeding was carried out on the same day as the fire and immediately after fire in the same burned plots simulating dispersion after fire (Figure 1d). In each plot, we randomly established 10 squared seeding units (30-cm side; Figure 1c). The seeding units were compound of two sets of 10 seeds, including two biogeographical seed provenances per species to test the post-burns recruitment responses to the conditions of each study site in relation to climate adaption. Provenance was defined as a territory with uniform ecological conditions in which seed sources or sites had similar phenotypic or genetic characteristics (Alía et al., 2005). They were chosen from the available store of the Department of Forest Genetic Resources of the Spanish Ministry of the Environment (Alía et al., 2009). We selected seeds from a provenance from colder and more humid (Wetter) and warmer and drier (Drier) regions for each species (detailed information in Table 2). An explanatory flow chart of the study design is observed in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Flow chart of the experiment

Sowing was carried out in spring 2016 at the soil-litter interface in each seeding unit. A total 5400 seeds were sown for the experiment. The procedure was done by marking small slots on the soil surface in 3-cm separated rows and then placing seeds on the soil surface. Wire cages were installed by covering seeding units to avoid seed/seedling predation, which can act as an important limiting factor for these individuals' recruitment dynamics (Sagra et al., 2017). We carried out quarterly monitoring from May 2016 to June 2017 by counting the number of new pine seeds that had germinated since the previous counting and pine seedling survival during each one. In this way we temporally tracked the seed germination and seedling establishment of the three pine species.

Table 2. Description of the provenances for the pine species used at each experimental site. Provenance: indicates the climate of the provenance *versus* the sowing stand. Code is the nomenclature used by the Department of Forest Genetic Resources of the Spanish Ministry of the Environment. Viability test is the percentage of seeds germinated from the seed supplier's controlled test.

Site	Species	Provenance	Origin	Code	Viability test (%)
PH	<i>P. halepensis</i>	Drier	Almeria, South Spain	ES13	90
		Wetter	Cazorla, Southeast Spain	ES16	94
PP	<i>P. pinaster</i>	Drier	Moratalla, Southeast Spain	ES18	98
		Wetter	Soria, North Spain	ES09	82
PN	<i>P. nigra</i>	Drier	Baza, South Spain	ES08	92
		Wetter	Burgos, North Spain	ES10	94

Pine seed germination was calculated by the percentage of the number of seeds that had germinated by the end of 1-year period. This percentage (Germ) was calculated of the 10 seeds included in each seeding unit for all the analysed factors (treatment, provenance).

$$Germ (\%) = \frac{n_{germ}}{N_{germ}} * 100 \quad (1)$$

where “Germ” is the germination rate for each factor in each seeding unit, “n_{Germ}” is the number of germinated seeds, “N_{Germ}” is the number of seeds per seeding unit and factor (which was always 10).

The survival percentage was estimated at two time points: (i) at the end of the first summer after burns (Survsumm), calculated from the seedlings that had survived through that season from those that had germinated immediately before; (ii) at the end of the 1-year study period (Survtot), calculated from the number of seedlings alive at the end of the study from those that had germinated throughout the study. Likewise until germination, these percentages were considered per factor in each seeding unit.

$$\text{Survsumm (\%)} = \frac{n_{\text{Survsumm}}}{N_{\text{Survsumm}}} * 100 \quad (2)$$

where “Survsumm” is the survival rate for each factor in each seeding unit, “n_{Survsumm}” is the number of seedlings per seeding unit and factor that were alive after first dry period, “N_{Survsumm}” is the number of seedlings per seeding unit and factor that germinated immediately before the dry period.

$$\text{Survtot (\%)} = \frac{n_{\text{Survtot}}}{N_{\text{Survtot}}} * 100 \quad (3)$$

where “Survtot” is the survival for each factor in each seeding unit, “n_{Survtot}” is the number of seedlings per seeding unit and factor that were alive at the end of the study, “N_{Survtot}” is the number of seeds per seeding unit and factor that germinated throughout the study.

Statistical analyses

Generalized linear models (GLM) were used to assess the effects of the factors and their interactions for all three sites: Treatment (Control, Pre and Post), Provenance (drier and wetter) and Treatment*Provenance. They were all tested for significant differences (P < 0.05) using one- and two-way analyses of variance (ANOVA). These analyses were run with the R statistical software (R Development Core Team, 2011). We also used the adjusted R-squared statistic to observe how well our models explained the observed variability. F-value and the Durbin-Watson statistics were used to test the residuals and to determine if there was any significant correlation based on the order in which they occurred in the data file. We used *Tukey's HSD (honest significant difference)* method to create confidence intervals for all the factor level means.

3 Results

The adjusted R^2 for the GLM test was higher than 35 for all the models (Table 3), except for the two survival models for *P. halepensis*, which showed an adjusted R^2 of 17 and 3.59 for *Survtot* and *Survsumm*, respectively. The GLM test (Table 3) gave significant differences in all the models (p -value <0.05) for the three species. It also indicated that the variable *Germ* was significant in the models for the three pine species for *Treatment*, *Provenance* and their interaction.

The control plots showed similar germination and survival levels between the individuals from the drier and wetter provenances (Figure 3), and this pattern is observed for the three species. However in the burned plots, both pre and post, some clear differences between the germination and survival rates of the drier and wetter provenances were observed. Survival and germination were higher in the drier than in the wetter provenance and for all three species.

Regarding treatments, the control plots had higher germination and survival levels for the three species than those plots at the burned sites. The Pre individuals displayed higher germination and survival rates than the Post ones. This difference came even more clearly from the comparison made between the Pre and Post plots, which were pair-wise for each provenance, where these differences were more noticeable.

Table 3: General Linear Models for all the variables in this study. *Germ*: number of pine seeds germinated at the end of the experiment; *Survsumm*: survival rate after the first summer *Survtot*: survival rate for the whole study period. *Treatment*: Control, Pre and Post; *Provenance*: drier and wetter.

	Statistics		Factor	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	F	P-value	
<i>Pinus halepensis</i>	Germ	R ²						
		Adjusted R ²	51.743	Treatment	24707.8	2	38.75	<0.001
		F	39.39	Provenance	29902.2	1	93.79	<0.001
		P-value	<0.001	Treatment*Provenance	8174.44	2	12.82	<0.001
	Durbin-Watson	1.8624						
	Survsumm	R ²	19					
		Adjusted R ²	17	Treatment	18419.1	2	17.07	<0.001
		F	8.09	Provenance	2121.11	1	3.93	0.049
		P-value	<0.001	Treatment*Provenance	1280.42	2	1.19	0.3077
	Durbin-Watson	18						
	Survtot	R ²	6.29					
		Adjusted R ²	3.59	Treatment	2580.14	2	2.59	0.0782
F		2.33	Provenance	2293.37	1	4.6	0.0334	
P-value		0.0441	Treatment*Provenance	947.723	2	0.95	0.3887	
Durbin-Watson	1.57							
<i>Pinus pinaster</i>	Germ	R ²	53.772					
		Adjusted R ²	52.444	Treatment	23901.1	2	43.7	<0.001
		F	40.48	Provenance	24500	1	89.6	<0.001
		P-value	<0.001	Treatment*Provenance	6943.33	2	12.7	<0.001
	Durbin-Watson	1.4878						
	Survsumm	R ²	35.969					
		Adjusted R ²	34.118	Treatment	20367.2	2	31.59	<0.001
		F	19.44	Provenance	8340.02	1	25.87	<0.001
		P-value	<0.001	Treatment*Provenance	2530.72	2	3.92	0.0215
	Durbin-Watson	1.0706						
	Survtot	R ²	47.516					
		Adjusted R ²	46.008	Treatment	35354.7	2	67.46	<0.001
F		31.51	Provenance	3576.92	1	13.65	0.0003	
P-value		<0.001	Treatment*Provenance	2346.94	2	4.48	0.0127	
Durbin-Watson	1.206							
Germ	R ²	59.574						
	Adjusted R ²	58.412	Treatment	68363.3	2	107.9	<0.001	
	F	51.28	Provenance	7220	1	22.79	<0.001	
	P-value	<0.001	Treatment*Provenance	5663.33	2	8.94	<0.001	
Durbin-Watson	1.2299							
Survsumm	R ²	78.133						
	Adjusted R ²	77.505	Treatment	82031.7	2	290.7	<0.001	
	F	124.34	Provenance	3155.07	1	22.36	<0.001	
	P-value	<0.001	Treatment*Provenance	2549.63	2	9.03	0.0002	
Durbin-Watson	1.7873							
Survtot	R ²	84.565						
	Adjusted R ²	84.122	Treatment	118058	2	469.8	<0.001	
	F	190.66	Provenance	1444.43	1	11.5	<0.001	
	P-value	<0.001	Treatment*Provenance	281.911	2	1.12	0.328	
Durbin-Watson	1.5163							

Figure 3. Analysis of Variance of the significant interactions between the variable Total Germination (Germ) and the significant factors and interactions: prescription (Treatment) and provenance for all three species *P. halepensis*, *P. pinaster* and *P. nigra*. Distinct small letters indicate the significant differences between the means of groups, for each variable and each species (Tukey's HSD method). Terms are as described in the text.

4 Discussion

The three sites design of our study allowed us to check how recruitment could be influenced by prescribed burn on these three pine species. Research into forest management using fire as a tool is one of the main concerns for Mediterranean ecosystems in a global change scenario (Doblas-Miranda et al., 2015). The temperatures recorded while monitoring prescribed fires indicated a low-moderate severity fire, with enough heat to affect the natural post-fire germination process (Martínez-Sánchez et al., 1995; Reyes and Casal, 1995). Our findings indicated a negative effect of prescribed fires on the recruitment of the three studied species. Although resilience to moderate fires of many pine species can favor pine stand regeneration (Calvo et al., 2008), severe fires have been shown to increase seedling growth due to greater post-fire nutrient availability (Eugenio et al., 2006). Increases in nutrients and water-extractable elements, however, may not be so decisive in seed germination and seedling growth in low-severity fires (Pereira et al., 2012). Our analysis presented higher germination and better establishment success rates in the control areas for the three species. So despite its adaptations to fire, even low intensity fire has negative effects on the recruitment of obligate seeder Mediterranean pines. The soil-plant interface was negatively impacted after fire passage in the short term when seed and seedling necessities are more vital (Gómez et al., 2004). Factors such as soil respiration, water repellence and predation are known to fluctuate and to create harsher conditions for seedlings to grow in (Espinosa et al., 2018; Plaza-Álvarez et al., 2017; Sagra et al., 2017). An increment in soil temperature and a reduction in soil respiration and moisture compared to the control areas have been reported in these same plots, which confirms this tougher environment for pine recruitment (Plaza-Álvarez et al., 2017).

Regarding *P. halepensis*, some studies have pointed out that wildfires significantly reduce the number of seedlings after fire compared to low and intermediate fire occurrences (Pausas et al.,

2003). Martín-Sanz et al., 2017, have also indicated how lower water supply from drought or post-fire conditions can lead to earlier dissemination. This can influence the resilience of these populations by altering canopy seed banks and recruitment after stand-replacing fires. A negative correlation between seedling survival and fire severity and ash deposition on soil has also been found (Izhaki et al., 2000; Reyes and Casal, 2004). This agrees with our results as the burned stands showed lower germination and survival rates than the control plots. In addition, within the burned area, the pine seeds exposed to fire displayed better performance in both germination and survival terms than those sown after fire. This finding can be attributed to a combination of ash effect and the encouragement of recruitment from low-severity fire (Ne'eman et al., 1993; Pausas et al., 2003; Reyes and Casal, 2004). The small number of seedlings in *P. halepensis* for the three treatments compared to the results of *P. pinaster* and a *P. nigra*, was noticeable, which pattern became even more obvious for survival after the first summer. This low seedling survival rate in *P. halepensis* after summer could be an effect of water stress during the dry period (which was especially dry in this area that year). Water stress is known to be one of the major constraints of seedling survival for pine species in the Mediterranean basin, and represents a sustainable forest management problem (Castro et al., 2002; Oliver, 2007; Rodríguez-García et al., 2011). Furthermore, the serotiny nature of *P. halepensis* would support these results where (in burned plots) the seeds exposed to fire obtained better results than those left unexposed (Hernández-Serrano et al., 2014).

Pinus pinaster showed negative fire-related effects in the burned units, which has also been observed when protection from scrubs disappeared after burns (Rodríguez-García et al., 2011). The same negative ash load effect has been reported for this species, which agrees with the lower

survival and germination rates that we obtained in the burned units (Izhaki et al., 2000; Vega et al., 2008).

P. nigra recruitment seemed to be the most affected by fire with more marked drops in the germination and survival rates than for the other two pine species. Some studies have reported a major negative effect of fire on *P. nigra* recruitment. Some of the reasons for this circumstance could include the reduced soil organic layer (Fontúrbel et al., 2011). A reduction in the soil organic layer due to fire can strongly affect seedling water availability for seedlings (Lucas-Borja et al., 2012). The masting feature of *P. nigra* is also noteworthy, which condenses successful recruitment years to these masting years, and could play a role when utilizing prescribed fire when natural dissemination occurs (Lucas-Borja et al., 2010). Although both the Pre and Post seeds and seedlings were grown on ash in our study, the Post (mimicking dispersion after fire) seeds seemed to perform much worse for all three species in both germination and survival terms. We believe that stimulation from fire heat may play a role that counteracts the effect of ash. Consequently, the seeds dispersed before fire may be exposed to a less negative effect than those not exposed to fire. Another study carried out by (Lucas-Borja et al., 2016) presented similar negative effects from burning on the regeneration rates in both pure and mixed stands of *P. nigra*. These authors also highlighted how *P. nigra* recruitment was extremely needful of the soil organic layer given the positive correlation between water availability and seedling performance (Lucas-Borja et al., 2012). For both *P. pinaster* and *P. nigra*, sufficient seed hydration during germination and water availability for seedlings may have permitted better germination and survival, which contrasts with *P. halepensis*, where it may have acted as a bottleneck for recruitment. This may be attributed to better root system development and would agree with the worse performance observed at the burned sites (Lee et al., 2004).

Regarding the results obtained for provenances, we observed that the provenances from drier areas obtained better germination and survival rates in the burned areas for all three pine species. In the control areas, no such difference was observed between the drier and wetter provenances. On the contrary in both the burned treatments (Pre and Post), the drier provenance seemed to enhance recruitment success. This same pattern was detected for Survival after summer and Survival after the whole study. However, differences between provenances were more marked for the species' emergence rates. Both *P. halepensis* and *P. pinaster* serotinies have been studied, with higher serotiny levels in the areas where fire recurrence was higher and for both species (Hernandez-Serrano et al., 2013). The better performance of the drier provenances only in the burned sites could also be an exaptation to the new environmental conditions that occurred in the burned area, which could more resemble those conditions in the areas where these provenances came from (Keeley et al., 2011; Knapp et al., 2009). This finding can indicate possible future circumstances that can take place in pine recruitment dynamics in a climate change context, which could improve fulfilling the management and conservation objectives in future scenarios predicted by IPCC (Garzón et al., 2011). However, more research is needed to obtain a complete overview of seasonal changes, such as response to stress due to burning outside natural burning and dispersion periods (Medlyn et al., 2002; Tapias et al., 2001). Different fire adaptation strategies to fire from these three species can also be a determinant to understand the role of provenances in prescribed fire responses (Richardson and Rundel, 2000). Therefore, adaptation to recurrent and low severity fires from *P. nigra* or serotiny and adaptation to medium severity or crown fires from *P. halepensis* and *P. pinaster* should be considered when accounting for these effects (Hernández-Serrano et al., 2014; Lucas-Borja et al., 2016). Even though an attempt to conserve natural forest genetic pools must be made a priority, the genuine poor genetic character of stands due to extensive

repopulations over the last century can make non native breeding or provenances an upright strategy to conserve the resilience and functionality of these stands (Millar et al., 2007; Willis et al., 2010).

5 Conclusions

This work intended to provide knowledge about the effects and consequences that prescribed fires can have on early recruitment in Mediterranean pine forests. Use of fire seemed to lower the chances of germination and survival in early stages of *P. halepensis*, *P. pinaster* and *P. nigra*. These three pine species responded negatively to low-moderate severity fires, especially *P. nigra*, and also mark a main difference between the seeds affected by fire and those that were not. The lower germination and early survival rates in the individuals not affected by fire may provide significant insight for prescribed fire planning, depending on the objectives to implement this tool. Prescribed fires can be a suitable tool for fuel reduction management on silviculture (i.e. fire breaks) or as an improvement for natural regeneration in certain circumstances. Use of dissimilar provenances to enhance performance in climate change scenarios may be necessary to adapt vegetation to climate shifts. Drier provenances appeared to perform better for all three pine species in the burned areas, which could be an indicator that these provenances (from harsher conditions) may be better adapted to the new post-fire conditions. However, comprehensive knowledge is still lacking to understand that the provenances from drier areas perform better under all the burned conditions. Further research is necessary to improve adaptive forest management. Understanding how prescribed fires may influence recruitment patterns is a key point to help forest managers and forest services with their management planning.

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